

EVOLUTION OF RESIDUAL STRESS AND DEFORMATION OF FIBER REINFORCED LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a meso/micro-mechanical study of fiber reinforced polymeric matrix cross-ply laminate during and after a high temperature curing process. The emphasis is on the generation and evolution of the curing induced residual stress/strain and its influence on the response under subsequently mechanical loading of the laminate. The cross-ply laminate is modeled by a representative volume element and the constituent materials are described by an elastic model for the fiber and a nonlinear viscoelastic model for the polymer matrix. The residual stress/strain fields at the ambient temperature immediately following the cool-down and their evolution with time are determined through the viscoelastic finite element discretization of the RVE with a special consideration given to the fiber/matrix interface region. The results indicate that the residual stresses decreases with time and tends to small asymptotic values after about 34 hours. However, the remaining residual strains still have significant influences on the damage evolution of the cross-ply laminate under subsequently superimposed tensile loading.

KEYWORDS: Cross-ply laminates, Fiber-reinforced polymeric composite, Meso/micro-mechanical modeling, Nonlinear viscoelastic analysis, Thermal residual stress/strain

INTRODUCTION

For various manufacturing processes of fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites, high temperature curing is required. When composites are cooled from their curing temperature to room temperature, residual stresses/strains are generated in the composites due to the mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the fiber and matrix constituents. It is a common practice in many current analyses of polymer composites to neglect the effects of processing induced residual stresses. However, the rationale for such an approximation is still unclear. There is no consensus as yet regarding the methodology to determine the processing induced residual stresses, e.g. see comments in a composite handbook [1]. In general, experimental measurement of residual stresses in composites is complicated and the results have been rather difficult to interpret [2]. An alternative is to attempt to predict residual stresses through meso/micro-mechanical modeling. In such an analysis a representative volume element (RVE) is constructed which represents the periodic structure of the laminate. The properties of each constituent, i.e. fiber and matrix, are then used in the RVE analysis. The analysis is often carried out by a numerical procedure such as finite element method (FEM).

A number of investigators [3-5] have used a micromechanical model to study the generation of residual stresses in metal matrix composites in which the matrices were assumed to be elasto-plastic materials. A few researchers, e.g. [6-7], have extended this methodology to polymer-based composites. In particular, the evolution of residual stresses with time due to viscoelasticity of the polymer matrix has been addressed in [7].

The curing induced residual stresses/strains of polymeric composite laminates is further investigated in this paper with focus on the effect of the temperature dependence of matrix properties and the influence of residual stresses/strains on the response of the laminate under subsequently applied mechanical loads. To find bounds on the magnitude of residual stresses generated during solidification process, three types of analysis are carried out. First, it is assumed that the polymer

matrix properties during cool-down are time-dependent (nonlinear viscoelastic) but temperature-independent. Second, the matrix properties are both time and temperature dependent. And third, the rate of cooling for both of the above analyses is varied to investigate the effect of cool-down rate on the generation of thermal residual stresses.

The numerical analysis of the laminate under thermal/mechanical loading is conducted through the nonlinear viscoelastic finite element discretization of the RVE with special consideration given to the fiber/matrix interface region. The results indicate that the higher the cooling rate, the higher are the residual stresses in the laminate. However, due to the viscosity of the polymer matrix, the residual stresses relax with time and asymptotically tend to small values irrespective of the different cooling rates, provided that no damage was induced in the laminate during the cooling process. The average shrinkage strains of the laminate are also time-dependent and approach an asymptotic value after the stress relaxation process. The effect of mechanical loading superimposed on the laminate after cooling to the ambient temperature is further investigated. This analysis considers a damage criterion for the matrix cracking, and the evolution of damage with the increased load is studied. It is found that both the location and load level at which damage initiates and propagates depend on the residual stress/strain distribution.

THE FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

1. Meso/micro-mechanical model of [0/90] cross-ply laminate

Figure 1(a) shows a meso/micro-mechanical representation of a thick cross-ply [0/90] laminate [8-9]. It consists of two *unit cubes*. Each unit cube contains a single fiber as shown by the cylindrical part in the figure and represents one unidirectional layer of the laminate. A unit cube has the same fiber volume fraction as the represented ply. Two stacked unit cubes with fibers in perpendicular directions can represent the 0/90 lay-up orientations. In practice, each layer of laminate may contain a number of fibers. The diameter of each fiber is of the order of a few microns, and the thickness of the layers is of the order of $100 \mu m$. Therefore for each unit cell a single fiber represents a homogenization of fibers in a ply, and the unit cell is of the order of the thickness of the ply. Thus, this two cell RVE model can be regarded as a 3 dimensional meso/micro-mechanical model of the cross-ply laminate. The cross-ply is assumed to be thick, i.e. there are many 0/90 plies alternately arranged in the thickness direction. Therefore, periodical boundary conditions are applied in all three coordinate directions for the micromechanical model. Only 1/8 of the model needs to be analyzed by the finite element method due to the symmetry of geometry and load conditions. In the analysis to follow, the fiber volume fraction was taken to be 52.5%, and is the same for each layer in the laminate.

Fig. 1 The meso/micro-mechanical model of cross-ply laminate.

The model is meshed with 8-nodes brick elements with a total of 1368 elements and 1799 nodes. There is a thin layer around the fiber, the thickness of which is 3% of the radius of the fiber. And the material of the interface is assumed to be the same as the matrix, see Fig.1(b).

2. Constitutive relations of the fiber and matrix

The fiber is assumed to be elastic with Young's modulus, $E_f=72,500 \text{ MPa}$, Poisson's ratio, $\nu_f=0.22$ and the coefficient of thermal expansion $CTE=5 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$. The stress-strain relation is given by:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = \frac{1}{E}[A]\{\sigma\} + \{\varepsilon_{th}\} \quad (1)$$

where $\{\varepsilon_{th}\}$ is the thermal strain.

The epoxy polymer matrix is modeled by a nonlinear viscoelastic model as in [10] and is summarized by the following expressions:

$$\{\dot{\varepsilon}_t\} = \{\dot{\varepsilon}_e\} + \{\dot{\varepsilon}_c\} + \{\dot{\varepsilon}_{th}\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{\dot{\varepsilon}_c\} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(a_i [A] \sigma_{eq}^{\alpha_i - 1} \{\sigma\} - b_i \{\varepsilon_{ci}\} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = E[A]^{-1} \{\dot{\varepsilon}_e\} \quad (4)$$

In the above, $\{\dot{\varepsilon}_t\}$, $\{\dot{\varepsilon}_e\}$, $\{\dot{\varepsilon}_c\}$, $\{\dot{\varepsilon}_{th}\}$, $\{\dot{\sigma}\}$ are the total strain-rate, elastic strain-rate, creep strain-rate, thermal strain-rate and stress-rate vectors (each contains six components), respectively. The material constants defined in Eqs (2) to (4) for the epoxy matrix were determined by tests at room temperature, and details can be found in [10]. In the following section, the temperature dependence of the material constants are determined.

3. Temperature dependence of material constants

For the epoxy resin used in this investigation, the glass transition temperature is 110°C (provided by the manufacturer). The curing temperature, 149°C , is higher than the glass transition temperature. Thermal transition temperatures, for example, the glass transition temperature, T_g , and the melting temperature, T_m , strongly affect the mechanical properties of polymers and their composites. The morphology of the polymer is also a determining factor [11-13]. Therefore, it would be more reasonable to consider the dependency of the material constants on temperature.

For the cross-linked epoxy polymer matrix in this study, the following relations are used.

(a) Poisson's ratio is assumed to be temperature independent[12].

(b) We consider the change of Young's modulus over the range from curing temperature to room temperature. The total temperature range can be divided into three regions. When $T \geq T_g + \Delta T_2$, the matrix is in liquid or rubbery state [12], and E is assumed to have a very small value, for example, for some polymers it is of the order of a few MPa, or $E(T) \approx (0.001 \sim 0.01)E(T_r)$, where $E(T_r)$ is the modulus at room temperature. The transition region around T_g is assumed to be $T_g - \Delta T_1 \leq T \leq T_g + \Delta T_2$, in which, E varies greatly. When $T \leq T_g - \Delta T_1$, the matrix is in solid state, and E changes slightly. Exponential functions are used for the last two regions, and the constants are determined approximately by using the data for similar polymers in refs [11-12]:

$$\begin{aligned}
E(T) &= E(T_r) \exp\left(-k_1 \frac{T - T_r}{T_g - \Delta T_1 - T_r}\right) & T \leq T_g - \Delta T_1 \\
E(T) &= E(T_g - \Delta T_1) \exp\left(-k_2 \frac{T - T_g + \Delta T_1}{\Delta T_1 + \Delta T_2}\right) & T_g - \Delta T_1 \leq T \leq T_g + \Delta T_2 \\
E(T) &= 0.01E(T_r) & T \geq T_g + \Delta T_2
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

For the current matrix we have, approximately,

$$\begin{aligned}
T_g &= 110^\circ C, \quad T_r = 23^\circ C, \quad \Delta T_1 = \Delta T_2 = 35^\circ C, \\
E(T_r) &= 2600 MPa, \quad E(T_g - \Delta T_1) = 0.7E(T_r), \quad E(T_g + \Delta T_2) = 0.01E(T_r), \\
k_1 &= 0.357 \text{ and } k_2 = 4.249.
\end{aligned}$$

(c) For a_i in Eq. (3) we assume,

$$\begin{aligned}
a_i(T) &= a_i(T_r) \exp\left(k_1 \frac{T - T_r}{T_g - \Delta T_1 - T_r}\right) & T \leq T_g - \Delta T_1 \\
a_i(T) &= a_i(T_r) \exp\left(k_2 \frac{T - T_g + \Delta T_1}{\Delta T_1 + \Delta T_2}\right) & T_g - \Delta T_1 \leq T \leq T_g + \Delta T_2 \\
a_i(T) &= a_i(T_r) \times 10^2 & T \geq T_g + \Delta T_2
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $a_i(T_r)$, is the value at room temperature. The constant b_i is assumed to be temperature independent. The values of coefficients a_i and b_i at room temperature are taken to be ($i = 2$):

$$\begin{aligned}
a_1 &= 5 \times 10^{-8} (MPa)^{-2}, & b_1 &= 0.01, \\
a_2 &= 1 \times 10^{-8} (MPa)^{-2}, & b_2 &= 1 \times 10^{-6}
\end{aligned}$$

(d) The CTE is assumed to change linearly with temperature with a slope of [12],

$$K = \frac{\alpha_l - \alpha(T_r)}{T_g - T_r} \tag{7}$$

where $\alpha(T_r) = 63 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$ and $\alpha_l = 139 \times 10^{-6}$.

4. Boundary conditions and damage criterion

Symmetric boundary conditions were applied to the boundary surfaces $X=0$, $Y=0$ and $Z=0$ (Fig.1b). A uniform temperature distribution was assumed in the analysis, therefore the periodic conditions at other three boundary surfaces are equivalent to the plane-remains-plane conditions, i.e.

$$u(1, Y, Z) = u(1, 0, 0), \quad v(X, 2, Z) = v(0, 2, 0) \text{ and } w(X, Y, 1) = w(0, 0, 1) \tag{8}$$

It is assumed that the epoxy matrix will crack when the maximum principal strain value is greater than 4% and a post-failure constitutive relation is introduced as in [8-9]:

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = \beta E [A]^{-1} \{\dot{\varepsilon}\} - \alpha \{\sigma\} \tag{9}$$

with $\beta = 0.0001$, $\alpha = 0.01$. Note that only the mechanical part of the total strain is considered in the damage criterion.

RESULTS

1. Generation and evolution of thermal residual stresses and deformation

The residual stresses σ_{zz} induced by cooling from the curing temperature of 149°C to 23°C at a cooling rate of 1.4°C/min are shown in Fig. 2. These results are based on the temperature-dependent material constants as specified in the previous section and the residual stress distribution is at the instant when reaching the room temperature. It can be seen that the maximum tensile stress is 33.68 MPa in the matrix near the interface and the maximum compressive stress is 61.89 MPa in the fiber. For the [0/90] cross-ply laminate the stress component σ_{xx} has the same maximum values and distribution as σ_{zz} . To find bounds on

Fig. 2 Residual stress (σ_{zz}) distribution in the model

the magnitude of residual stresses generated, two other types of analysis are carried out. First, a slower cooling rate of 0.15°C/min is specified. Second, it is assumed that the polymer matrix properties during cool-down are temperature-independent. For the slower cooling rate of 0.15°C/min, the distribution is similar to Fig. 2 but with maximum tensile stress of 27.22 MPa in the matrix and maximum compressive stress of 50.44 MPa in the fiber. Therefore, a faster cooling rate results in higher residual stresses. When the material constants at the room temperature are used for the entire temperature range, much higher values of residual stresses are obtained. The maximum tensile stress in the later case is 42.69 MPa and compressive stress is 77.7 MPa for the cooling rate of 1.4°C/min, and the corresponding values for the slower rate of 0.15°C/min are 32.01 MPa and 59.04 MPa. Since the modulus of an epoxy material increases with the decrease of temperature, the results from the temperature-independent constants overestimate the residual stresses in the composite laminate. An elastic solution is obtained by assuming $\{\dot{\epsilon}_c\} = 0$, in Eqs. (2) and (3). For this elastic solution, the maximum tensile stress in the matrix is 52MPa and the maximum compressive stress in the fiber is 101MPa, irrespective of the rate of cooling.

Following the cooling to the room temperature, creep and relaxation occur due to the viscoelastic properties of the epoxy matrix. The change of the stress/strain in the matrix causes the change of the stress/strain in the elastic fiber in order to reach a new state of balance for the cross-ply laminate. The numerical analysis was continued for 2500 minutes (≈ 42 hrs) while the temperature was held at 23°C. Figures 3 and 4 show the evolution of the maximum tensile stress in the matrix and the maximum compressive stress in the fiber, respectively. The time 0 in the figures corresponds to the instant when the curing temperature reached 23°C. In the legend of the figures, “TD” refers to the results with *temperature dependent* material constants, and “TI” refers to the results with *temperature independent* material constants. It can be seen that both tensile and compressive stresses are decreasing with time. The cooling rate affects the initial residual stress values. However, irrespective of the cooling rate, the residual stresses asymptotically tend to small values. For example, after 2500 minutes, the maximum tensile stresses are 6.32 MPa and 5.76 MPa, and the maximum compressive stresses are 10.12 MPa and 9.40 MPa, for the cooling rate of 1.4°C/min and 0.15°C/min, respectively. For the purpose of comparison, the results of temperature-independent constants are also presented in the figures. They show a similar trend and the residual stress values after 2500 minutes for both the fast and slow cooling rates are not much different than the time-independent ones.

Fig. 3 Evolution of the maximum tensile stress in the matrix

Fig. 4 Evolution of the maximum compressive stress in the fiber

The shrinkage of the laminate can be illustrated by the average strain (global strain). For the current $[0/90]_n$ cross-ply laminate the average shrinkage strain is the same in the X- and Z-axes directions and can be obtained from the following equation:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_L^S = \frac{-w(0,0,1)}{L} \quad (10)$$

where L is the length of the micro-mechanical model in the Z-direction and $w(0,0,1)$ is the displacement of the surface $Z=1$. Figure 5 shows the evolution of the average shrinkage strain with the passing of time. It is noted that a fast cooling rate results in a higher shrinkage strain when the laminate is cooled to room temperature. The thermal shrinkage strain gradually recovers and asymptotically tends to a small value irrespective of the cooling rate. Again, the result from the temperature-independent material constants shows a similar trend to that of the temperature-dependent material constants, however, the magnitude of the shrinkage strain is overestimated.

Fig. 5 The evolution of shrinkage strain $\bar{\varepsilon}_{zz}$

The average shrinkage strain discussed above is actually the average strain over the volume of RVE. However, it is the local stress/strain state in the fiber or matrix that will influence the damage response of the laminate. In composite laminates, the local strain in the fiber and matrix may be quite different due to the “concentration” effect of fibers embedded in an homogeneous matrix. Furthermore, only the mechanical part (residual strain) of the total strain would influence the response under a subsequent superimposed mechanical loading. At each point within the RVE, the total strain $\{\varepsilon_t\}$, mechanical part of the strain $\{\varepsilon_m\}$ and the thermal strain $\{\varepsilon_{th}\}$ have the following relation:

$$\{\varepsilon_m\} = \{\varepsilon_t\} - \{\varepsilon_{th}\} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 6 The distribution of first principal strain

All the above strains can be obtained from the results of the finite element analysis. The mechanical part of the strain results from the mismatch of the thermal strains of the fiber and the matrix and it evolves with time due to a combined action of creep and stress relaxation. Figure 6 shows the distribution of the first principal strain of the strain vector $\{\varepsilon_m\}$ in the RVE at 2700 minutes after cooling to room temperature at 1.4°C/min (using temperature dependent material constants). It can be seen that the highest residual principal strain reaches 3.5% in the matrix near the fiber/matrix interface – a rather high value.

2. Results of subsequent uniaxial tensile loading

The previous results indicate that the residual stresses and the average shrinkage strain tend to small values after a certain period of time, however, the local residual strains in the RVE model are still quite significant. To study the influence of residual stresses/strains on the response of the laminate under subsequently applied mechanical loads, the damage evolution in the matrix under a uniaxial tensile loading in Z-direction is investigated. The procedure is as follows. After keeping the laminate at room temperature for 2700 min, a global tensile strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}$ is superimposed to the model. This is achieved by specifying a displacement at the surface $Z=1$. The analysis is carried out in the micromechanical model with the residual stress/strain state. The load is applied up to $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}=1.5\%$ (superimposed value) at a strain rate of $10^{-5} s^{-1}$. At each time step the damage zone of the matrix is determined using the criterion described earlier.

The evolution of the damage zones (represented by red color) in matrix is shown in Fig. 7(a). When the global strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}=0.2\%$, the damage starts at the fiber/matrix interface near the fiber in 90° ply (fiber along X-direction). Then the damage propagates along two orientations. One is the expansion along the hoop direction of the interface, and the other one is along the axial direction of the interface (X-direction). At $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}=0.5\%$, the damage occurs at the upper edge of the surface $Z=1$. This damage zone on the plane $Z=1$ does not progress further with the increased strain (transverse matrix crack), but the damaged zone along the fiber/matrix interface propagates further in the X-direction at about $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}=1.0\%$. It is noted in the lower part of the RVE (0° ply, where the fiber is in the loading direction) no damage has yet occurred.

Fig 7(a) Damage evolution with residual stress/strain

Fig. 7(b) Damage evolution without residual stress/strain

For the sake of comparison, Fig.7(b) shows the damage evolution under the same uniaxial tensile loading but neglecting the residual stress/strain introduced in the curing process. It can be seen that the location and the strain level at which damage initiates, and the evolution of the damage are different in these two cases. This indicates that although the residual stress relaxes to a small value

after a period of time, the local residual strains could still have a significant influence on the subsequent mechanical loading.

CONCLUSIONS

The evolution of thermal residual stress/strain induced during curing process and their influence on the subsequent mechanical loading have been investigated through a viscoelastic finite element analysis of a micromechanical model of a cross-ply laminate. The following conclusions are drawn from the present study:

- The generation of the residual stresses strongly depends on the cooling rate. A higher cooling rate results in a higher initial residual stresses. Hence, it is advisable to reduce the cooling rate during the curing process to avoid possible matrix cracking when first reaching the ambient temperature. The model with temperature independent constants over-predicts the residual stresses.
- A stress relaxation process takes place in polymer composites after the temperature has dropped to the ambient one. The residual stresses decrease with time. In addition, they asymptotically tend to a small value irrespective of the effects of the rates.
- The maximum shrinkage is reached at the completion of the cooling process. A higher cooling rate results in a higher shrinkage strain. However, most of the shrinkage strain is recovered with time and it asymptotically tends to a small value irrespective of the effects of the different cooling rates.
- Although the residual stress and the global shrinkage strain are small after a period of time, the local residual strains could still have a significant influence on damage initiation. They affect the damage evolution under subsequent mechanical loading. The location and the global strain level of the damage initiation, and the evolution of the damage are different for cases with or without consideration of the residual stress/strain.

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